

METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING NARRATION IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7024403>

Abstract. *This article outlines methods for teaching narration in elementary school, provides examples of working with texts.*

Keywords: *narration, types of narrations, speech and thought activity, oral speech, micro-themes, speech development.*

МЕТОДИКА ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИЗЛОЖЕНИЮ В НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ШКОЛЕ

Аннотация. *В этой статье излагаются методы обучения изложению в начальной школе, приводятся примеры работы с текстами.*

Ключевые слова: *изложение, виды изложений, речемыслительная деятельность, устная речь, микротемы, речевое развитие.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important tasks facing the teacher is teaching pupils to fully communicate, accurately express their thoughts. Primary school pupils have a limited amount of words, monotonous syntactic constructions.

Their speech consists of short sentences of the same type with a weakly expressed connection between them. The text they create often breaks up into short chopped phrases of a monotonous structure. Therefore, it is very important to teach children to feel the word, to know synonymy, to use morphological forms and syntactic constructions correctly.

The main types of work aimed at the development of coherent written speech, i.e. contributing to the formation of a comprehensive ability to create a text in writing are narrations and essays.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Narration — retelling the text (oral or written), presented in the form of educational work for the development of pupils' speech, the formation and consolidation of skills in stylistic construction and spelling.

Work with text goes in two directions:

- ✓ forming skills to analyze the finished text;
- ✓ training in retelling the text in oral and written form (writing narrations), compiling one's own statements (writing essays).

Systematic work on the text gives students the opportunity to observe, comprehensively analyze the studied lexical and grammatical phenomena in their organic relationship.

Working with the finished text in the Russian language lessons is the most important tool that contributes to the speech development of students. It develops in schoolchildren the ability to analyze the text (determine the topic, main idea, match the title to the topic and the main idea, determine the type of text, highlight micro topics, divide the text into parts, draw up a plan) and convey its content. An important exercise in the development of coherent speech of younger students is narration, i.e. written retelling of the finished text - a sample (artistic, journalistic, popular science).

The narration of the text is a combination of two types of speech activity - the perception of someone else's text and its reproduction.

In preparation for the narration, an oral spelling analysis of the relevant words is carried out. After writing the presentation, students are given the task - to check the spelling of words that have spellings for the rule being studied.

RESULTS

Learning the presentation should be started with a narrative text that has a clear plot, close and understandable to a child of this age. The story should have a small number of episodes. All words must be clear in their meaning, syntactic constructions are available for use in children's speech.

The requirements for presentation must be adhered to:

✓ independence of pupils in the narration of the text (the sample should not be memorized and completely copied);

✓ using vocabulary, turns of speech, syntactic constructions taken from the sample in the text of the narration;

✓ completeness of the transfer of essential points - compliance with the sequence of narration, cause-and-effect dependence of the main facts.

There are several types of narration:

1. **Descriptive.** The main goal of a descriptive narration is to teach to see the chain of signs of a person or object, to increase observation, to consolidate the skills of remembering the smallest details.
2. **Narrative.** Particular attention in the narrative text should be given to the storyline. The points of the plan will be a sequence of certain actions that form the event backbone of the heard story.
3. **Condensed.** When writing it, the details recede into the background. It is necessary to highlight the main thing in the text, catch its semantic message and write down the main arguments.
4. **Reasoning.** Such a presentation is a real creative work. It captures the main thing, not concentrating on the little things.

The teacher prepares the children to work on the narration according to the finished plan. Pupils must read the questions on the board correctly and understand their content; answer exactly the question of the plan; when retelling and writing, arrange their answers sequentially, in accordance with the order of the questions in the plan.

In the work on the narration, children develop the skill to build a simple sentence. Pupils learn the correct word order in a sentence, learn to put a period at the end of a sentence and delimit it in meaning from other sentences. To strengthen writing skills, it is necessary to teach children to use in the presentation those words that they understand and know how to write correctly.

Compiling an answer to a plan question is a synthetic work. In this case, the teacher should pay more attention to the correct arrangement of words in the sentence. Often children insert a word to answer in place of a question word in a plan question: *Who did the grandfather give to the children? (The hedgehog was presented to the children by the grandfather).* In this case, this word order is not suitable. The teacher prompts the children to arrange the words in the

sentence according to the model of this sentence in the story, i.e. *Grandfather gave the children a hedgehog.*

Mandatory for the prevention of errors is the pronunciation of words difficult for children in syllables. Before writing some words, you can use a split alphabet: children will analyze by syllables, compose and read a word or a short sentence.

Thus, all types of narrations according to the finished plan are mainly aimed at developing and improving two qualities of pupils' coherent speech:

1) the ability to correctly understand the question of the plan and answer it correctly and sufficiently fully;

2) the ability to establish a logical connection between the parts of the story, express it using the necessary lexical means (suddenly, once, therefore, since then, etc.) and arrange it graphically by correctly dividing it into paragraphs.

DISCUSSION

To plan a story means, first of all, to divide it into parts. For the correct division into parts, it is necessary to establish the sequence of events, the order of their development, the boundaries between them and their mutual connection.

The heading process is an important learning activity, the purpose of which is for students to correctly and accurately identify the topic or main idea of the heading part of the story.

Let us single out the main principles of the narration methodology:

1. Getting to know the text.

The teacher reads the text, the pupils listen to it carefully, follow the storyline. The teacher highlights the main parts of the text with pauses. The presented text can be read by pupils. Definition of the topic of the text.

2. Conversation on the content of the text on teacher questions.

3-4 questions are posed on the content of the text in order to determine whether the students understood everything correctly, understood what they read, and established cause-and-effect relationships. Determining the type of text, its structure.

3. Rereading the text.

The text is read no more than 2 times so that pupils do not memorize it.

4. Drawing up a text plan.

Logical and compositional division of the text into parts, their heading. The presentation plan is written on the **board**.

5. Spelling preparation, vocabulary work.

Analysis of the meanings of words and their spelling, observation of the use of visual means of the language in the text, building of the most important syntactic constructions.

Writing on the board of words and phrases that require special attention of pupils.

6. Preliminary retelling of text fragments. Selection of key words.

The teacher offers to retell individual fragments, asks: "How would you tell about it yourself?", "How is this thought expressed, how it is said in the text of the writer?". Questions like these encourage pupils to express their thoughts on their own. At this stage of the work, individual proposals are collectively compiled, if necessary – fragments of the text. **Key words for each item in the plan** are written **on the board**.

7. Oral retelling of the text.

Several pupils orally retell the text according to the plan and key words.

8. Analysis of oral retelling and its improvement.

Collective correction of shortcomings, clarification of individual points. If necessary, the text is read again.

9. Independent writing of the narration.

CONCLUSIONS

To work on mistakes, the teacher analyzes the presentations and classifies them taking into account:

- ✓ accuracy and consistency in the transmission of the content of the text;
- ✓ errors in the construction of sentences;
- ✓ misuse of words;
- ✓ the most gross and typical spelling and punctuation errors.

Thus, the presentation teaching methodology includes the following areas of work with children:

- Work on the sound side of speech
- Vocabulary work (enrichment, clarification and activation of vocabulary)
- Working on sentences and phrases.
- Development of coherent speech.

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